

WORK VALUES, ENGAGEMENT AND SATISFACTION OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 8

Pages: 902-916

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1810

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11177152

Manuscript Accepted: 04-17-2024

Work Values, Engagement and Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers

Buenafe C. Cadampog,* Oldric J. Licaros

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Amidst the Covid-19 pandemic, educators play an essential role in instructing students. This study aimed to assess the correlation between work, values, engagement, and satisfaction among secondary school teachers in the municipality of Aleosan during the School Year 2022-2023. The study's results reveal that the extent of work values, work environment, work interaction, and work activities amid the pandemic show that they are always engaged in their work in terms of vigor, absorption, and dedication. Teachers are constantly engaged in their work in terms of vigor, absorption, and dedication. The study revealed that teachers indicate satisfaction with their work from the perspective of intrinsic and extrinsic factors, and it shows a significant relationship between work values and the engagement of standard school teachers. The result also found that the teacher respondents performed well and took responsibility in compliance with their desire to be fulfilled with their work. The pandemic did not hinder them from performing their tasks.

Keywords: *work values, engagement, satisfaction, COVID-19 pandemic*

Introduction

What values do teachers hold on to, how they engage, and what they feel in their workplaces are particularly important in helping build a nation's future. As key facilitators of knowledge, it is, thus, indispensable to find how comfortable they are while at work. Teachers who are engaged in their profession and committed to students and their learning play a crucial role in the development of students (Mart, 2013). On the other hand, satisfied teachers, according to Sahito and Vaisanen (2017), can fulfill more effectively their duties to facilitate all stakeholders in achieving the development and success of the nation through knowledge, skills and their implications.

However, with the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic, keeping the teachers engaged and satisfied posed a major challenge. Their feeling of engagement and satisfaction at work was influenced by the change of the teaching environment and the challenges brought by it (Misu, 2020). Keeping teachers as strategic human resource of the country more and more engaged and satisfied to their job no matter the situation needs to be constantly addressed. Faced with this scenario, teachers adapted themselves to the situation by keeping themselves engaged despite the challenges spawned by the pandemic. Indispensably, they capitalized on their work values in order to get through those challenges and emerge satisfied while performing their duties and responsibilities. Filipino teachers, indeed, had to face work and life changes during the pandemic situation (Baloran & Hernan, 2020).

The ability to retain and engage employees is now, more than ever, a major strategic issue for organizations in the context of a pandemic (Parent-Lamarche, 2022). As Asian Development Bank (2021) emphasized, supporting teachers ensures that educational challenges in the Philippines will be addressed. Helping them maintain or strengthen their work values, engagement and satisfaction will ensure quality of teachers which has the greatest impact on improving student learning outcomes (Simeon, 2021).

In the context of the researcher, the teachers in her school followed guidelines and policies mandated by the Department of Education, directing its personnel to get themselves focused on their work, maintaining their work values and engagement intact and remaining satisfied despite the challenges brought about by the pandemic. However, some major concerns such as heavy workloads, too many ancillary works given to them, and the anxiety spawned by the health crisis have managed to surface. The pandemic and pivot to emergency remote teaching resulted in a sudden, large drop in teachers' sense of success (Kraft et al., 2020).

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the work values, engagement, and satisfaction of the secondary school teachers in the Municipality of Aleosan, Province of Cotabato for the School Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the work values of the secondary school teachers in terms of core values, work environment, work interactions, and work activities?
2. What is the level of work engagement of the secondary school teachers in terms of vigor, absorption, and dedication?
3. What is the level of work satisfaction of the secondary school teachers in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic aspects?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the work values and engagement of secondary school teachers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the work values and satisfaction of secondary school teachers?
6. Is there a significant relationship between engagement and satisfaction of secondary school teachers?

Methodology

This section presents the procedures to be followed in carrying out the study. It explains the research process used in collecting and analyzing data. The chapter is structured into research design, locale and respondents of the study, research instrumentation, data

gathering procedures, data processing and analysis and statistical tools and treatment of data.

Research Design

The researcher used the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive design was used to describe and identify the work values, engagement, and satisfaction of secondary school teachers. It also used correlational method to determine the significant relationship between work values, engagement, and satisfaction of the respondents.

Participants

The study was conducted in the Municipality of Aleosan, Province of Cotabato. The respondents of the study were all 168 secondary school teachers in the Municipality of Aleosan, North Cotabato for the SY 2022-2023.

Instruments

The instrument used in this study was a researcher-made survey questionnaire. Its contents were primarily based on the readings of the related literature and studies which were taken from books, journals, and the internet. All questions were written in English.

The survey questionnaire was divided into four parts. Part I consisted of items regarding the demographic profile of the respondents which included sex, age, educational attainment, position, and years of teaching. It was done for profiling purposes only. Part II contained items that measured the work values of the secondary school teachers in terms of core values, work environment, work interactions, and work activities. Part III consisted of items that determined the level of work engagement of the respondents in terms of vigor, absorption, and dedication. Part IV contained a 20-item survey that measured the level of job satisfaction of the respondents in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic aspects. Parts II, III and IV employed a modified questionnaire developed from Work Values Inventory (2006), Schaufeli and Bakker's (2003) Utrecht Work Engagement Scale, UWES – 17, and Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire by Weiss, Dawis, England, and Lofquist (1967).

Procedure

The researcher secured the approval from the Dean of Graduate School of Notre Dame of Midsayap College and Division Superintendent of the Department of Education through the Cluster Head of the secondary schools in the municipality of Aleosan. Upon their approval, the researcher secured an endorsement letter from the Division, a copy of which was furnished to the supervisors and school principals of the secondary schools in the municipality of Aleosan for the schedule of the administration of the instruments. The researcher set a schedule to meet the respondents in each school for the conduct of the study. Health and safety protocols were observed during the conduct of the study. The researcher with the help of the principal and teachers informed the respondents about the purpose of the study and a survey questionnaire was distributed to the respondents. Questionnaires were personally retrieved from the respondents immediately after they finished answering the questionnaire.

Statistical Tools

The data were treated with the use of appropriate statistical tools. Weighted mean and standard deviation were computed in problems 1, 2, and 3 to determine the work values, level of engagement, and level of satisfaction of the respondents. In problems 4, 5 and 6, Spearman rho was used to test the significant relationship between the work values, engagement, and satisfaction of the secondary school teachers.

Results

This section presents the results of the study. The data are presented in tabular form which include the work values of the secondary school teachers in terms of core values, work environment, work interactions, and work activities, level of work engagement of the secondary school teachers in terms of vigor, absorption, and dedication, and level of work satisfaction of the secondary school teachers in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic aspects during the time of the pandemic.

Level of Work Values of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Core Values and Work Environment During Pandemic Time

Level of work values of the secondary school teachers in terms of core values and work environment during pandemic time. Table 1 shows the results of the level of work values of the secondary school teachers in terms of core values.

Items 1 and 8 on being able to meet my goals and “being able to care for and trust self and others” are both rated by the respondents as very important work values after they earned the highest means of 4.55 and 4.52, respectively interpreted as always with a standard deviation of 0.61 and 0.60.

Moreover, the results also reveal that the core value which the respondents treated as moderately important was having influence and power over others. This core value obtained the lowest mean of 3.28 interpreted as often with a standard deviation of 1.20.

Generally, the overall mean of the level of work values of the secondary school teachers in terms of core values was 4.17 interpreted as very often or important with an overall standard deviation of 0.79.

Table 1. *Level of Work Values of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Core Values and Work Environment During Pandemic Time*

<i>Work Values</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Core Values			
My core values include....			
1. Being able to meet my goals	4.55	0.61	Always
2. Having time for family, work and play	4.30	0.86	Very Often
3. Having control of my own destiny	4.05	0.90	Very Often
4. Being able to have an impact to others.	4.26	0.70	Very Often
5. Being able to stand up for my own beliefs.	4.37	0.61	Very Often
6. Telling the truth and knowing that others are also telling the truth.	4.49	0.61	Very Often
7. Having control over others.	3.28	1.20	Often
8. Being able to care for and trust self and others.	4.52	0.60	Always
9. Believing in your core beliefs.	4.48	0.63	Very Often
10. Having influence and power over others.	3.37	1.18	Often
Overall Mean	4.17		Very Often
Overall Standard Deviation		0.79	

4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Very Often; 2.50-3.49 Often; 1.50-2.49 1.00-1.49 Never

In addition, Table 1.1 presents the level of work values of the secondary school teachers in terms of work environment.

The table reveals that Item 8 which states that work is organized and has a specific set time obtained the highest mean of 4.28 interpreted as very often or important in the work environment of the participants with a standard deviation of 0.74. Item 3 stating that work is intellectually challenging to me gained the second highest mean of 4.24 interpreted as very often with a standard deviation of 0.76. The respondents looked at this work value in their work environment as Important.

In addition, item 4 on convenience and ease in commuting can be enjoyed earned the third highest mean of 4.07 interpreted as very often or important with a standard deviation of 0.81.

Table 1.1 *Level of Work Values of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Core Values and Work Environment During Pandemic Time*

<i>Work Values</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
B. Work Environment			
I value work environment where.....			
1. Many things happen at one time.	3.97	0.77	Very Often
2. The potential to make a lot of money is high	3.63	0.93	Very Often
3. Work is intellectually challenging to me.	4.24	0.76	Very Often
4. Convenience and ease in commuting can be enjoyed.	4.07	0.81	Very Often
5. I have knowledge of what is going to happen day after day.	3.89	0.88	Very Often
6. There are few disruptions throughout the day.	3.71	0.91	Very Often
7. There are less pressures to get things done.	3.87	0.86	Very Often
8. Work is organized and has a specific set time.	4.28	0.74	Very Often
9. I set my own schedule and plan how and when I do my work.	4.17	0.82	Very Often
10. Work is not set to a specific time schedule.	3.17	1.17	Often
Overall Mean	3.90		Very Often
Overall Standard Deviation		0.87	

4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Very Often; 2.50-3.49 Often; 1.50-2.49 1.00-1.49 Never

On the other hand, item 10 which states that work is not set to a specific time schedule had the lowest mean of 3.17 interpreted as often or moderately important with a standard deviation of 1.17. Finally, the results revealed that the respondents considered the work value in terms of the work environment as Important, as evidenced by its overall mean of 3.90, interpreted as Very Often with a standard deviation of 0.87.

Level of Work Values of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Work Interactions and Work Activities

Table 2 shows the level of work values of the secondary school teachers in terms of work interactions and work activities. The findings reveal that item 9 on working together is important obtain the highest mean of 4.65 interpreted as always with a standard deviation of 0.58. For the respondents, this work value in terms of work interactions was very important. Obtaining the second highest mean of 4.41 was item 3 which states that I socialize with my co-teachers. This value is interpreted as very often or important with a standard deviation of 0.73.

Moreover, item 8 everyone can help and support others obtain the third highest mean of 4.40 interpreted as very often or important with a standard deviation of 0.68. Emerging as the item with the lowest mean was item 1 which states that I can compete with others. It recorded a mean of 3.32 with a standard deviation of 1.13. Finally, the overall mean of the level of work values of the secondary teachers in terms of work interactions is 4.12 interpreted as very often or important with an overall standard deviation of 0.85.

In terms of work activities, Table 2 reveals that item 4 are helping people obtain the highest mean of 4.45 interpreted as very often with a standard deviation of 0.66. Among the respondents, this work value was very important.

Table 2. *Level of Work Values of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Work Interactions and Work Activities*

<i>Work Values</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
C. Work Interactions			
I value work interactions where.....			
1. I can compete with others.	3.32	1.13	Often
2. My co-teachers come from different ethnic backgrounds	3.76	1.09	Very Often
3. I socialize with my co-teachers	4.41	0.73	Very Often
4. There are good leaders managing the organization	4.31	0.74	Very Often
5. There is strong management.	4.23	0.82	Very Often
6. Information is not held back from employees.	3.82	0.97	Very Often
7. I am acknowledged for my work and contribution	4.01	0.92	Very Often
8. Everyone can help and support others.	4.40	0.68	Very Often
9. Working together is important.	4.65	0.58	Very Often
10. I can count on my co-teachers.	4.26	0.81	Very Often
Overall Mean	4.12		Very Often
Overall Standard Deviation		0.85	
<i>4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Very Often; 2.50-3.49 Often; 1.50-2.49 1.00-1.49 Never</i>			

The findings reveal that item 9 on working together is important obtain the highest mean of 4.65 interpreted as always with a standard deviation of 0.58. For the respondents, this work value in terms of work interactions was very important. Obtaining the second highest mean of 4.41 was item 3 which states that I socialize with my co-teachers. This value is interpreted as very often or important with a standard deviation of 0.73.

Moreover, item 8 everyone can help, and support others obtain the third highest mean of 4.40 interpreted as very often or important with a standard deviation of 0.68. Emerging as the item with the lowest mean was item 1 which states that I can compete with others. It recorded a mean of 3.32 with a standard deviation of 1.13. Finally, the overall mean of the level of work values of the secondary teachers in terms of work interactions is 4.12 interpreted as very often or important with an overall standard deviation of 0.85.

In terms of work activities, Table 2.1 reveals that item 4 are helping people obtain the highest mean of 4.45 interpreted as very often with a standard deviation of 0.66. Among the respondents, this work value was very important. Earning the second highest mean is item 3 which states use imagination and creative talents to produce results. Its mean of 4.23 was interpreted as very often or very important with a standard deviation of 0.73. Ranked third are item 5 work on new and innovative products or projects and item 8, hone my skills for searching new information which earned the same mean of 4.22 interpreted as very often or very important with a standard deviation of 0.73 and 0.74, respectively.

Table 2.1 *Level of Work Values of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Work Interactions and Work Activities*

<i>Work Values</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
D. Work Activities			
I value work activities that...			
1. I require interaction of data and information	4.11	0.72	Very Often
2. Are mentally or physically challenging.	4.21	0.74	Very Often
3. Use imagination and creative talents to produce results.	4.23	0.73	Very Often
4. Are helping people.	4.45	0.66	Very Often
5. Work on new and innovative products or projects.	4.22	0.73	Very Often
6. Have a lot of physical activity.	3.82	0.81	Very Often
7. Have daily interaction with the public.	3.91	0.86	Very Often
8. Hone my skills for searching new information.	4.22	0.74	Very Often
9. Allow me to take risks.	3.79	0.90	Very Often
10. Provide many different tasks during the day.	3.95	0.88	Very Often
Overall Mean	4.09		Very Often
Overall Standard Deviation		0.78	
<i>4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Very Often; 2.50-3.49 Often; 1.50-2.49 1.00-1.49 Never</i>			

However, earning the lowest mean of 3.79 is item 9 allow me to take risks interpreted as very often or very important with a standard deviation of 0.90. Overall, work values of teachers in terms of their work activities revealed a mean of 4.09 interpreted as Very Often or Very Important with a standard deviation of 0.78.

Level of Work Engagement of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Vigor, Absorption and Dedication

Table 3 shows the level of work engagement of the secondary school teachers in terms of vigor, absorption, and dedication.

Table 3. *Level of Work Engagement of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Vigor*

<i>Work Engagement of Teachers</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Vigor			
1. At my work, I persevere even when things do not go well.	3.98	0.75	Very Often
2. At my job, I am very mentally resilient.	4.02	0.68	Very Often
3. I can continue working for very long period of time.	3.92	0.77	Very Often
4. When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work.	4.10	0.85	Very Often
5. At my job, I feel strong and vigorous.	4.11	0.72	Very Often
6. At my job, I feel strong and vigorous.	4.11	0.75	Very Often
Overall Mean	4.00		Very Often
Overall Standard Deviation		0.75	

4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Very Often; 2.50-3.49 Often; 1.50-2.49 1.00-1.49 Never

In terms of Vigor of teachers, Table 3 revealed that item 5 which states that at my job, I feel strong and vigorous obtained the highest mean of 4.11 interpreted as very often or highly engaged with a standard deviation of 0.72. Further, it revealed that item 4 when I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work obtained the second highest mean of 4.10 interpreted as very often or highly engaged with a standard deviation of 0.85.

However, the table showed that item 6 stating at my work, I feel bursting with energy emerged with the lowest mean of 3.87 interpreted as Very Often or Highly Engaged with a standard deviation of 0.75. Finally, in terms of Vigor of teachers, Table 3 reveals an overall mean of 4.00 interpreted as Very Often or Highly Engaged with an overall standard deviation of 0.75.

In terms of Absorption as work engagement of the secondary school teachers, Table 3.1 reveals that item 6 stating “time flies fast when I am working” obtained the highest mean of 3.98 interpreted as Very Often or Highly Engaged with a standard deviation of 0.93. Obtaining the second highest mean is item 1 stating it is difficult to detach myself from my job with a mean of 3.95 interpreted as Very Often or Highly Engaged with a standard deviation of 0.87.

Table 3.1 *Level of Work Engagement of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Vigor, Absorption and Dedication*

<i>Work Engagement of Teachers</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
B. Absorption			
1. It is difficult to detach myself from the job.	3.95	0.87	Very Often
2. I get carried away when I am working.	3.82	0.86	Very Often
3. I am immersed in my work.	3.91	0.78	Very Often
4. I feel happy when I am working intensely.	3.87	0.91	Very Often
5. When I am working, I forgot everything else around me.	3.42	1.08	Often
6. Time flies fast when I was working.	3.98	0.93	Very Often
Overall Mean	3.83		Very Often
Overall Standard Deviation		0.91	

4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Very Often; 2.50-3.49 Often; 1.50-2.49 1.00-1.49 Never

Item 5, when I am working, I forget everything else around me got the lowest mean of 3.42 interpreted as often or moderately engaged with a standard deviation of 1.08. Finally, Table 3.2 on Absorption earned an overall mean of 3.83 interpreted as Very Often or Highly Engaged with a standard deviation of 0.91.

In terms on Dedication as part of work engagement of the teachers, Table 3 shows that item 4 which states that “I am proud of the work that I do” earned the highest mean of 4.44 interpreted as very often or highly engaged with a standard deviation of 0.67.

Table 3.2 *Level of Work Engagement of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Vigor, Absorption and Dedication*

<i>Work Engagement of Teachers</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
C. Dedication			
1. I find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose.	4.30	0.66	Very Often
2. I am enthusiastic about my job.	4.20	0.63	Very Often
3. My job inspires me.	4.28	0.71	Very Often
4. I am proud of the work that I do.	4.45	0.63	Very Often
5. To me, my job is challenging.	4.44	0.67	Very Often
Overall Mean	4.33		Very Often
Overall Standard Deviation		0.66	

4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Very Often; 2.50-3.49 Often; 1.50-2.49 1.00-1.49 Never

With the second highest mean was item 5 which states that to me, my job is challenging. It obtained a mean of 4.44 interpreted as very often or highly engaged with a standard deviation of 0.67. Table 3 also shows that item 2 on I am enthusiastic about my job ranked the lowest after it obtained a mean of 4.20 interpreted as very often or highly engaged with a standard deviation of 0.63. Finally, the overall mean of the secondary school teachers’ level of work engagement in terms of Dedication reached 4.33 interpreted as very often or highly engaged with an overall standard deviation of 0.66.

Table 4 Level of Work Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in terms of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Means

Table 4 shows the level of work satisfaction of secondary school teachers in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic means. In terms of intrinsic means, item 6 on the feeling of accomplishment I get from the job obtained the highest mean of 4.20 interpreted as Agree or Very Satisfied with a standard deviation of 0.69. Item 7 stated as “the chance to do things for other people” got the second highest mean of 4.16 interpreted as Agree or Very Satisfied with a standard deviation of 0.70. Further, item 9 on “the chance to do something that makes use of my abilities” earned the third highest mean of 4.10 interpreted as Agree or Very Satisfied with a standard deviation of 0.73. Item 4 on “the chance to be “somebody” in the school”, however, got the lowest mean of 3.69 interpreted as Agree or Very Satisfied with a standard deviation of 1.03. Overall, the level of work satisfaction of secondary school teachers in terms of intrinsic means earned an overall mean of 3.98 interpreted as Agree or Very Satisfied with an overall standard deviation of 0.80.

Table 4. *Level of Work Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Means*

<i>Work Satisfaction</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
A. Intrinsic Means			
My work satisfaction includes...			
1. Being able to keep busy all the time.	3.86	0.86	Agree
2. The chance to try my own methods of doing the job.	4.05	0.73	Agree
3. The chance to try my own methods of the doing the job.	3.96	0.72	Agree
4. The chance to be “somebody” in the school.	3.69	1.03	Agree
5. Being able to do things that do not go against my conscience.	3.89	0.93	Agree
6. The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job.	4.20	0.69	Agree
7. The chance to do things for other people.	4.16	0.70	Agree
8. The chance to tell people what to do.	3.94	0.80	Agree
9. The chance to do something that makes use of my abilities.	4.10	0.73	Agree
10. The freedom to use my own judgement.	3.93	0.79	Agree
Overall Mean	3.98	0.79	Agree
Overall Standard Deviation		0.80	
<i>4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Very Often; 2.50-3.49 Often; 1.50-2.49 1.00-1.49 Never</i>			

Moreover, Table 4.1 reveals the level of work satisfaction of secondary school teachers in terms of extrinsic means. The table revealed that item 7 which states the way my co-workers get along with each other got the highest mean of 4.19 interpreted as agree or very satisfied with a standard deviation of 0.80. Gaining the same interpretation of agree or very satisfied were item 1 stating the way my school head handles his/her workers and item 2 on the competence of my school in making decisions as they obtained means 4.16 and 4.10, with standard deviations of 0.79 and 0.77, respectively.

Table 4.1 *Level of Work Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Means*

<i>Work Satisfaction</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
B. Extrinsic Means			
My work satisfaction in terms of extrinsic means includes...			
1. The way my school head handles his/her workers.	4.16	0.79	Agree
2. The competence of my school in making decisions.	4.10	0.77	Agree
3. The way school policies are put into practice.	4.13	0.77	Agree
4. My pay and the amount of work I do.	3.97	0.98	Agree
5. The chances for advancement on my job.	3.94	0.83	Agree
6. The working conditions.	3.98	0.85	Agree
7. The way my co-workers get along with each other.	4.19	0.80	Agree
8. The praise I get for doing a good job.	3.98	0.92	Agree
9. The material support (i.e. printing supplies) given to me.	3.98	0.92	Agree
10. The technical assistance (i.e. training’s, workshop) given to teachers in the school.	4.04	0.85	Agree
Overall Mean	4.07	0.79	Agree
Overall Standard Deviation		0.84	
<i>4.50-5.00 Always; 3.50-4.49 Very Often; 2.50-3.49 Often; 1.50-2.49 1.00-1.49 Never</i>			

Further, item 5 stating the chances for advancement on my job got the lowest mean of 3.94 interpreted as agree or very satisfied with a standard deviation of 0.83. The table, finally, revealed the overall mean of 4.07 interpreted as Agree or Very Satisfied with an overall standard deviation of 0.84.

Relationship Between Work Values and Engagement of Secondary School Teachers

Table 5 shows the relationship between work values and engagement of secondary school teachers. Table 5 further reveals that the relationship between work values and engagement of secondary school teachers yielded p-values that are less than the 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between work values and the engagement of secondary school teachers is rejected.

Table 5. Relationship Between Work Values and Engagement of Secondary School Teachers

Variable	Engagement of Secondary Teachers								
	Vigor			Absorption			Dedication		
Work Values	r-value	p-value	Description	r-value	p-value	Description	r-value	p-value	Description
Core Values	0.520**	0.000	Reject null	0.510**	0.000	Reject null	0.514**	0.000	Reject null
Work Environment	0.594**	0.000	Reject null	0.573**	0.000	Reject null	0.552**	0.000	Reject null
Work Interactions	0.563**	0.000	Reject null	0.512**	0.000	Reject null	0.541**	0.000	Reject null
Work Activities	0.684**	0.000	Reject null	0.596**	0.000	Reject null	0.632**	0.000	Reject null

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Relationship Between Work Values and Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers

Table 6 presents the relationship between work values and the satisfaction of secondary school teachers. As shown, the work values and the satisfaction of secondary school teachers generated p-values that are less than the 0.01 level of significance. It can be noted that the variables are not significantly related to each other. Hence, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between the work values and the satisfaction of secondary school teachers is rejected.

Table 6. Relationship Between Work Values and Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers

Variable	Satisfaction					
	Intrinsic Means			Extrinsic Means		
Work Values	r-value	p-value	Description	r-value	p-value	Description
Core Values	0.549**	0.000	Reject null	0.501**	0.000	Reject null
Work Environment	0.617**	0.000	Reject null	0.579**	0.000	Reject null
Work Interactions	0.602**	0.000	Reject null	0.509**	0.000	Reject null
Work Activities	0.694**	0.000	Reject null	0.532**	0.000	Reject null

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 7 presents the relationship between engagement and satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Table 7. Relationship Between Engagement and Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers

Variable	Satisfaction					
	Intrinsic Means			Extrinsic Means		
Engagement	r-value	p-value	Description	r-value	p-value	Description
Vigor	0.724**	0.000	Reject null	0.564**	0.000	Reject null
Absorption	0.700**	0.000	Reject null	0.554**	0.000	Reject null
Dedication	0.610**	0.000	Reject null	0.540**	0.000	Reject null

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table shows that a significant relationship exists between engagement and satisfaction of secondary school teachers as evidenced by the p-values which are less than the 0.01 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship that exists between engagement and satisfaction of the secondary school teachers is rejected.

Discussion

This section presents the discussion of the results of the level of the work values of the secondary school teachers in terms of core values, work environment, work interactions, and work activities, level of work engagement of the secondary school teachers in terms of vigor, absorption, and dedication, level of work satisfaction of the secondary school teachers in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic aspects during the time of the pandemic, the significant difference in the level of work values, work engagement, and satisfaction of the secondary school teachers when grouped according to selected demographic profile, and the significant relationship between work values, engagement, and satisfaction of secondary school teachers.

Level of Work Values of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Core Values and Work Environment During Pandemic Time

Regarding the level of work values of the respondents in terms of their core values, the study reveals that being able to meet their goals was the first highest important. This indicates that the goals that the respondents set as teachers serve as their guide in promoting work values. Teachers give importance with their work as they practiced their professions to have a better output and to satisfy their work as well. This supports the findings of Ritchie et al (2021) demonstrating that the perception of successful agency, as a dimension of hope, contributes to life satisfaction.

The results also reveal that being able to care for and trust self and others is very important for the respondents. Being cared by everybody especially within the vicinity of work is important. Teachers felt that they are loved and cared by means of trusting them in all aspects especially in teaching. Being cared for and trust self others implies that looking after their welfare and that of others form a huge part of their work value. They, too, consider gaining and keeping faith and confidence with themselves and the people around them as very important. They put premium on maintaining good relationship with people they work with where care and trust can grow and flourish. This finding supports Good Therapy (2019) explaining that “people who are able to meet their own physical and emotional

needs are typically better equipped to take care of others”. The findings were also congruent to the research of Baker (2020) that demonstrated practicing self-care and wellness as having a big impact on how first-year teachers feel throughout the school year. Further, Cardinal and Thomas (2016) stressed that self-care helped each person fulfill their potential. Finally, the same findings echo that of Abdulhaevna et al. (2018) underscoring that self-trust level determines a person’s orientation on altruism, egoism, and social responsibility.

However, the respondents have not put as much weight on having influence and power over others rating it as a moderately important component of their inner core to demonstrate value in their workplace. This indicates that the teacher-respondents do not operate at work with much compulsion. They do not affect their colleagues and learners in a negative sense in their actions and behavior as professionals. This finding is not in consonance with the research data of Cotnoir et al. (2014) that suggested that teacher influence is manifested through building relationships, passion for their work, mentoring their students through modeling, having high expectations of their students, and their ways going “above and beyond” in their work.

Level of Work Values of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Work Environment

In terms of work environment, the study reveals that work being organized and having a specific set time is rated by the teacher-respondents as important. This implies that the respondents put school matters in place and proper perspective at an appointed time. This also means that the respondents maintain order in their classroom, as well as manage their projects, meet deadlines, and solve problems which thus help them gain efficiency and develop their skills on time management in the classroom. This finding is in consonance with Fleming (2011) who claimed that individuals who can accomplish tasks within the stipulated time frame can make their life improved and balance not only in their organization as well as among their peers and family. The finding also supports the study of Lualhati (2019) who concluded that teachers practice scheduling, goal setting, prioritizing tasks, managing paperwork, and managing interruptions to manage their time.

Moreover, the teacher-respondents considered the item on work as intellectually challenging to them as important. This means that the teachers acknowledge that they need to put more effort into their teaching by designing highly relevant content knowledge and pedagogical approaches that facilitate teaching and learning, by contextualizing their teaching and learning activities to the learning needs and styles of their learners, among others. This indicates, further, that they consider teaching as no mere task, but as a profession that requires intellectual rigor, appropriate skills set, and character. These findings are echoed in Meador (2020) who claimed that teaching is extremely difficult and draining—no one with actual teaching experience would tell you otherwise. Being a teacher takes patience, dedication, passion, and the ability to do more with less. Those committed to the profession do so simply because they want to be difference-makers. The same findings are echoed by Hewitt (2017) who asserted that a teaching career is highly challenging, intellectually demanding, and emotionally rewarding.

Finally, in terms of the work environment, the study reveals that experiencing convenience and ease in commuting from home to school is important among the teacher-respondents. This indicates that the respondents have expressed their need to feel good even while they travel to work for them to consistently do good at work. Their way to their workplace should provide them comfort which will enable them to function well as teachers. This finding is in consonance with that of Mallillin et al. (2020) who found that the participants in their study prefer convenience above any other factors while traveling. Moreover, the time spent on commuting to and from the workplace represents not only a physical but also a psychological transition from home to work and vice-versa. Also time spent commuting does not belong to any of the domains in particular (Burch & Barnes-Farrell, 2020). Studies have indicated that employees' likelihood of being more irritable and susceptible to poor concentration and self-control at work or home are higher if they experience a strenuous ride to work or to home, respectively (Wiese et al., 2020).

Level of Work Values of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Work Interactions and Work Activities

Regarding work interactions, the study discloses that the respondents rated working together is important as a very important work value to them. This means that the teacher-respondents put a value on teamwork and accomplishing school tasks together. This finding supports Boakye (2015) who stressed that people working in teams function more efficiently, are less prone to stress, and such individuals make a greater effort in their work since it provides quality services to customers, boosting the productivity of employees as well as the individual, prompting trust and a spirit of cooperation among members, improving the relationship.

The study also reveals that teachers considered socializing with their co-teachers to be important. This implies that the teacher-respondents find interacting with their fellow teachers as a significant activity that enhances their social skills and enriches their experiences. As members of the professional organization, the teachers essentially talk to each other on matters that can help them grow professionally or personally. This is not a surprise since the fundamental task of education is to form people who will be able to integrate socially and then take on responsibilities in the groups they belong to (Petrovai et al., 2012). This finding supports Terziev and Vasileva (2022) who claimed that interaction with friends, family relationships, and afterward school play the important role with whose support people learn to follow rules, to be rewarded for their work, and to learn how to behave in public places – all constituting examples of socialization that allow a person to function in their culture. Further, the same finding is in consonance with Pescaru (2019) who stressed that socialization develops the individual’s ability to self-educate, to manage himself to discern between good and evil, to know how to choose between the moral attitudes that are assessed by society negatively and those which allow for adequate

social cohabitation.

Moreover, in terms of work interactions, the study showed that the teachers view “everyone can help and support others” as important to them in their work as teachers. This indicates that the teachers acknowledge that they do not exist on their own and that they need one another for strength and inspiration. This finding corroborates with that of Jones et al., (2013) who perceived colleague support as a strong predictor of retention plans.

In terms of work activities, helping people is one indicator that the teachers rated as important. This indicates that the teacher-participants acknowledge working together or collaborating as playing a key role in building relationships among teachers so that they feel part of a professional community and derive personal fulfillment from their work. The main findings indicate that collaborative action needs to be an essential part of teachers’ work in an inclusive school (Lakkala, et al., 2021).

In addition, the study revealed that the teachers considered the use of imagination and creative talents to produce results as very important. This implies that for teachers to be productive and gain more added value in their workplace, they need to be more imaginative and creative. They should not settle for the basic knowledge and skills they possess, but more importantly, they should learn to explore and avoid doing the same things all over again. The finding supports Susilo et al. (2021) who emphasized that creativity is one of the skills that teachers must possess. Creativity makes them inspired in their learning. Creative teachers make class fun so that students like learning. It also helps teachers design learning that is different from what is usually done. Successful teachers are those with imagination.

The study also showed working on new and innovative products or projects as very important among the teacher-respondents. This indicates that teachers need to consider focusing their energies and resources on new and innovative initiatives as well for their learners or for the school so they can appropriately respond to the needs of their learners or to the demands of the times. Song, Kim, Chai and Bae (2014) suggested that an innovative school climate has a positive impact on teachers’ knowledge sharing and work engagement and influences teachers’ knowledge creation practices in a positive sense.

Regarding searching for new information as part of the teacher-respondents’ work activities, the study found that the respondents keep on honing their skills on that aspect since they consider it very important in making their performance at par with the standards in their field. This indicates that the respondents enhance their skills in searching for practical reasons. Possessing ICT skills or searching for new information is directly related to teachers’ motivation to work (Barni et al., 2019), job satisfaction, the development of innovative learning designs, and engaging learners (Zee & Koomen, 2016) and contributes to overall well-being (Zee & Koomen, 2016). This finding is in consonance with Rieh et al. (2016) who stressed that the teachers’ skill in searching for new information starts with the notion that information is the basis for human learning in today’s information-rich environments. It is associated with the common practice of information searching related to performing learning tasks in formal education contexts as well as work-life or everyday life.

Level of Work Engagement of the Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Vigor, Absorption and Dedication

On Vigor

In terms of the level of work engagement of the respondents, the study reveals that they are highly engaged at their job for feel strong and vigorous. This indicates that they possess high levels of energy, vitality, and flexibility in school. Further, this implies that they feel strongly involved in their work as teachers and experience a sense of significance, enthusiasm, and challenge. As it is natural to them, they perform their jobs with much energy and strength. The finding goes well with Sittar (2020) who concluded that vigor has a positive correlation with job performance. In the study of Briones et al. (2021), which investigated the relationship between work engagement, job satisfaction, and work performance of 340 LSPU faculty, they found out that faculty members often felt strong and vigorous. Oftentimes, they persevered even if they experienced challenges; full of energy; and they can continue working for very long periods at a time. The teaching force often remained vigorous despite the rigors of their work. The faculty employees have high levels of energy while working for the institution; therefore, the support they are receiving from the University officials propels them to stay focused at work. Their desire to attend to the needs of the learners with vigor serves as their motivation to perform the tasks expected of them which enables them to be engaged in the profession (Laguador,2013).

Moreover, the study revealed that the teachers are highly engaged in their work since they feel like going to work upon getting up in the morning. This indicates that the teachers are full of enthusiasm and energy for their work as molders of the youth. This enthusiasm manifested by the teachers indirectly predicted students’ mastery goal orientation through student-perceived support for social relatedness and autonomy (Frommelt et al., 2021). This finding supports Wenström et al. (2018) whose study revealed that the teacher-participants were very interested in their work. They wanted to share how they experienced enthusiasm in their work. Their enthusiasm manifested as their willingness to develop their skills and expertise, and shown in their dedication, good job performance, and positive feelings about their work. The finding is also aligned with Uusiutti (2017) who emphasized that these enthusiastic employees who are willing to develop the job and their own expertise are needed in the workplace and that their enthusiasm manifested itself in ways that can be assumed to improve the quality of education and well-being in the work community (Keller et al., 2016).

On Absorption

Regarding teachers' work engagement in terms of absorption, the study showed that the respondents are highly engaged at work as they experience that time flies when they are working. This implies that they are so totally engrossed with their work that they do not notice time passing by anymore. This kind of engagement of teachers can be attributed to several aspects. In the two experiments conducted Kawabata by and Chatzisarantis (2022), it was revealed that enjoyment of the task was essential to perceive time passing faster regardless of different tasks and the effort level, and the relationship between task enjoyment and the perceived speed of time was moderated by perceived effort. The findings of their study indicate that task nature and effort level should be considered simultaneously to understand the relationship between task enjoyment and time perception in an ecologically valid situation. In addition, subjective experience of time is influenced by multiple factors such as emotions (Liu & Li, 2020; Uusberg et al., 2018) and motivation (Gable & Poole, 2012) and attention (Woehrle & Magliano, 2012). Further, according to the study of Briones et al. (2021), respondents noticed that time flies when they are working. It is evident that they sometimes forget everything else around them and get carried away when they are working.

Finally, the study reveals that the teachers are highly engaged in their work since they find it difficult to detach themselves from their job. This means that the teachers are so attached to their work that they pour out their focus and attention to it. They often feel happy when they are working intensely and often immersed in their work; hence they often find it difficult to detach themselves from the job. This indicates, further, that their dedication and commitment to their work is tight and strong. However, Vallance (2022) has expressed detaching oneself from one's job could help realize that he is not defined by my work and has a life outside of it too. In addition, he emphasized the benefits of detachment instantly. Mood was better throughout the day and working much faster and improving work quality were observed (Vallance, 2022). A study by Korpela, Kinnunen, Geurts, de Bloom and Sianoja (2016) found that detaching from work increases levels of energy at work and vigor and decreases exhaustion.

On Dedication

In terms of dedication, the study reveals that the teacher-respondents are highly engaged with their work since they express their pride of their work. This means that despite the demands of their job as teachers, they still find fulfillment and sense of ownership or belongingness to their profession. The finding supports the study conducted by Briones et al. (2021) that stressing that teachers were found to be always inspired by their job and proud of the work they do. They were eager about their job as they felt a sense of meaning and purpose because of a challenging job.

Also, the study reveals that the respondents are highly engaged to their work as teachers since they consider their job as challenging. This indicates that the teachers face difficulties in various aspects to include mental, psycho-social, physical, and even emotional. This implies that amidst these challenges, the teachers are able to manage and carry out themselves professionally as they continue to treat these challenges not as reasons to give up but as platforms to become even more engaged into their work. The finding is in the same vein as that of Robosa et al. (2021) who claimed that most teachers are significantly challenged by lack of resources, handling of students, and the submission and workloads, and the adjustments they make with the emergence of the digital age. However, in their study, they pointed out that teachers gain positive experiences despite stress and burnout, that includes their passion, relationships built, and the fulfillment of their duty.

The study also revealed that the teachers are highly engaged in their work which they attribute as full of meaning and purpose. This indicates that the teachers feel energetic and inspired at work more specifically inspired about the subject they teach and being inspired about teaching in general (Keller et al. 2016). Their inspiration also extends to mean their interactions and teaching styles as well as their non-verbal communication and presentation in teaching situations. Kunter et al. (2013) emphasized that teacher enthusiasm has a positive influence on student learning, performance, motivation and on teaching quality. Respondents work throughout their full potentials to give supports to students needs with meaning and purpose.

Level of Work Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers in Terms of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Means

Intrinsic

In terms of intrinsic means, the study reveals that the teachers are very satisfied specially on the feeling of accomplishment they get from the job. This means that the teachers feel accomplished when they get things done in school. When they are satisfied with their accomplishments in school, other school matters are positively affected. They affect their students' performance. Their sense of accomplishment leads towards school improvement, quality education, and student satisfaction. The finding collaborates with Baluyos et al. (2019) who revealed that the teachers were highly satisfied with their job, and their work performance was very satisfactory.

In addition, the study reveals that the chance of the teachers to do things for other people makes the teachers very satisfied at work. This indicates that the teachers manifest other-centeredness. Clearly, they just do not do their job to satisfy themselves solely, but they do it for others' welfare as well. This implies that they feel very satisfied when they cause some desirable changes in behavior among their students, inspire their colleagues, or collaborate with their community on some worthwhile endeavors.

Extrinsic

In terms of extrinsic means, the study that the teacher-respondents were very satisfied as their co-workers get along with each other. This indicates that when they work together, they create a better working environment for them which will eventually produce a better learning experience for their learners. In that way, they become more comfortable and committed and feel like they belong to each other.

As regards their school heads' way of handling them as workers, the study revealed that the teacher-respondents were very satisfied. This indicates that their school heads manage the school efficiently and productively, given the human and financial resources of the school. For instance, their school heads empower them as teachers by involving them in the planning and decision-making of the school. This implies that their school heads create and maintain good working conditions in their school. The finding is in consonance with Simmons (2019) who pointed out that productive schools have school administrators who dedicate a significant amount of time to planning and overseeing instruction; are extremely visible in the school and remain loyal to the learning environment. Teachers have high expectations of school leaders in maintaining a supportive environment through collaboration, caring, and encouraging teachers (Nethels, 2010). However, Aquino et al. (2021) stressed that the very productive performance of teachers stays the same, regardless of whether the school heads exhibit a very high degree of authentic leadership.

The study, finally, reveals that the teacher-respondents are very satisfied in terms of the competence level of their school policies that are put into practice. This indicates that the teacher-respondents are satisfied with their administrators, co-teachers, and other school personnel including the students and the community who have demonstrated competence in deciding on important school matters. They, too, see decision making not as a management function by itself but as a collaborative work in conducting work, distributing resources, and planning short-term and long-term programs, projects, and activities of the school. This finding affirms Kumschick, et al. (2020) who claimed that decision-making is a process of reasoning, during which teachers must make use of their pedagogical knowledge while taking into account the students' abilities and motivation and preferably all school concerned and policies are put into practiced by administrators and staff of every school.

Relationship Between Work Values and Engagement of Secondary School Teachers

The relationship between work values and engagement of secondary school teachers yielded p-values that are less than the level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significance relationship between work values and the engagement of secondary school teachers is rejected. The relationship between the work values and engagement of secondary school teachers implies high significant based on the result of the variables like core values, work engagement, work interactions and work activities of the teachers to the engagement of secondary school teachers.

Relationship Between Work Values and Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers

The work values and the satisfaction of secondary school teachers generated p-values that are less than the level of significance. It can be noted that the variables are not significantly related to each other. Hence, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant relationship between the work values and the satisfaction of secondary school teachers is rejected. It shows that the relationship between work values and satisfaction of secondary school teachers implies high significance based on the results of the different variables like core values, work environment, work interactions and work activities to the satisfaction of the secondary school teachers in terms of intrinsic and extrinsic means.

Relationship Between Work Values and Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers

A significant relationship exists between engagement and satisfaction of secondary school teachers as evidenced by the p-values that are less than the significance level. Hence, the null hypothesis stating that no significant relationship exists between engagement and satisfaction of the secondary school teachers is rejected. It shows that the relationship between engagement and satisfaction of secondary school teachers implies high significance based on the result of the variable in engagement, such as vigor, absorption, and dedication to the intrinsic and extrinsic means of satisfaction of teachers in secondary school.

Conclusion

Based on the results and findings of the study, the following conclusions were made on the Work Values, Engagement and Satisfaction of Secondary School Teachers that there is a significant relationship between engagement and satisfaction of secondary school teachers. The respondents of the Aleosan Secondary school agreed that they are satisfied with their work and truly engaged in their profession amidst of the COVID-19 pandemic situations. Respondent -teachers observed their work values, engaged so much with their work and they agree that they are satisfied with their work. Overall, this study provide important insights into the work values, engagement and satisfaction of secondary school teachers that amidst of pandemic teacher-respondents perform well their responsibility in accordance with their will to fulfill their work. Pandemic is not the hindrance to them to perform their task as well. However, teachers keep on managing everything despite of all the challenges brought by pandemic like heavy workloads, too many ancillary work given by the department and anxiety spawned by the crisis because of the courage and integrity to keep moving with heart to the learners benefits.

Considering the conclusions of the study, the researcher highly recommends the following: (1) Teachers who are not satisfied with their work or in the field of teaching should undergo seminars on how to handle herself/himself in relation to his/ her work especially nowadays that are still facing COVID-19 pandemic especially in remote areas of Aleosan. (2) School administrators should make a school-based intervention program for the secondary school teachers that can help to improve the school performance base on the teachers' needs. (3) The Department of Education should recommend programs and training for teachers on how to adopt the new teaching strategies in enhancing education in the department.

References

- Adeyemo, K.S., Schoole, C. and Cueno, C.G. (2015) The Use of the Job Enrichment Technique for Decision-Making in Higher Education: The Case of the Philippines. *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 13, a645
- Aguado, C. L., Garcia, O. B., Laguador, J. M., Deligero, J. C. L. (2015). Teaching Performance and Extent of Work Values among Faculty Members in one Asian Maritime Academy. *International Journal of Management Sciences* Vol. 5, No. 12, 2015, 805-816.
- Alfes, K., Shantz, A.D., Truss, C. and Soane, E.C. (2013), "The link between perceived human resource management practices, engagement and employee behavior: a moderated mediation model", *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 330-351.
- Angeles, V. N. P., Saludo, A. K. M., Virtus, L. M. R., and Win, M. T., (2015) Job Satisfaction and Performance level of Employees of Ajinomoto Philippines Corporation Lucena Branch <https://lpulaguna.edu.ph/wpcontent/uploads/2016/08/Job-Satisfaction- Level-OfEmployees-Of-Ajinomoto-Philippines-Corporation-Lucena-Branch.pdf>
- Artacho, E., Martínez, T., Martín, L., Marín, J., & García, G. (2020). Teacher training and lifelong learning - The importance of digital competence in the encouragement of teaching innovation. *Sustainability*, 12, 2852. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12072852>
- Baloran, E. T. & Hernan, J. T. (2020). Crisis Self-Efficacy and Work Commitment of Education Workers among Public Schools during COVID-19 Pandemic. Preprints (www.preprints.org)
- Bakotić D., (2016). Relationship between job satisfaction and organisational performance, Crossref,Croatia, <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2016.1163946>
- Bhagwandeem, T. P. (2021). Relationship between Intrinsic Job Satisfaction, Extrinsic Job Satisfaction, and Employee Turnover Intentions (Order No. 28315669). Available from Publicly Available Content Database. (2488229734). <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/relationship-between-intrinsic-jobsatisfaction/docview/2488229734/se-2?accountid=193930>
- Biggs, A., Brough, P. and Barbour, J.P. (2014), "Strategic alignment with organizational priorities and work engagement: a multi-wave analysis", *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, Vol. 35 No. 3, pp. 301-317.
- Boakye, E. (2015). The Impact of Teamwork on Employee Performance. Research Gate. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.4959.8804
- Bravo, A. K. B., Baloloy, J. I., Beunafloor, N. B. & Tus, J. (2021). Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Job Burnout and Job Satisfaction of Public School Teachers in the Philippines. *International Journal Of Advance Research And Innovative Ideas In Education*. IJARIE-ISSN(O)-2395-4396 Vol-7 Issue-3 2021
- Breevaart, K., Bakker, A.B., Hetland, J., Demerouti, E., Olsen, O.K. and Espevik, R. (2014), "Daily transactional and transformational leadership and daily employee engagement", *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 87 No. 1, pp. 138-157.
- Briones, M. R., Yazon, A. D., Sarmiento, M. B., Ang-Manaig, K., Buama, C. A. C., Tesoro, J. F. B. (2021). Examining the Work Engagement, Job Satisfaction, and Performance of Faculty in One State University in the Philippines. *PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION* (2021) 58(5), ISSN 1553 – 6939.
- Buckman, D. G. (2017). Job Satisfaction: A Study of the Relationship between Right-to-Work Policy and Public School Teachers' Perceptions <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=job+satisfaction+studies&pg=4&id=EJ1162584>.
- Burch, K. A., & Barnes-Farrell, J. L. (2020). When work is your passenger: Understanding the relationship between work and commuting safety behaviors. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 25(4), 259–274. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000176>
- Christian, M.S., Garza, A.S. and Slaughter, J.E. (2011), "Work engagement: a quantitative review a test of its relations with task and contextual performance", *Personnel Psychology*, Vol. 64 No. 1, pp. 89-136.
- Costa, P.L., Passos, A. and Bakker, A.B. (2015), "Direct and contextual influence of team conflict on team resources, team work engagement, and team performance", *Negotiation and Conflict Management Research*, Vol. 8 No. 4, pp. 211-227.
- Ćulibrk, J., Deliđ, M., Mitrović, S., & Ćulibrk, D. (2018). Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment and Job Involvement: The Mediating Role of Job Involvement. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 132. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00132>

- Deci, E. L. (1971). Effects of externally mediated rewards on intrinsic motivation. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 18, 105–115.
- Demaki, G.O. (2012). Business recovery strategies in the economic crisis of recession in Nigeria. *An International Multidisciplinary Journal Ethiopia*, 6, 1-24.
- Fute, A.; Oubibi, M.; Sun, B.; Zhou, Y.; Xiao, W. (2022). Work Values Predict Job Satisfaction among Chinese Teachers during COVID-19: The Mediation Role of Work Engagement. *Sustainability*, 14, 1353. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14031353>
- Gawke, J.C.L., Gorgievski, M.J. and Bakker, A.B. (2017), “Employee intrapreneurship and work engagement: a latent change score approach”, *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, Vol. 100, June, pp. 88-100.
- Gültekin, O. (2019). Social Capital's Effect on Physical Education and Teachers' Job Satisfaction <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=Job+Satisfaction+Studies&id=EJ1202089>
- Gutermann, D., Lehmann-Willenbrock, N., Boer, D., Born, M. and Voelpel, S.C. (2017). “How leaders affect followers’ work engagement and performance: Integrating leader-member exchange and crossover theory”, *British Journal of Management*, Vol. 28 No. 2, pp. 299-314.
- Haj, S. J. & Jubran, A. M. (2016). The Extent of Principals' Application of the Transformational Leadership and Its Relationship to the Level of Job Satisfaction among Teachers of Galilee Region <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=job+satisfaction+studies&pg=5&id=EJ1099552>
- Hameed, F., Ahmed-Baig, I., & Cacheiro-González, M. L. (2018). Job satisfaction of teachers from public and private sector universities in Lahore, Pakistan: a comparative study. *Economics & Sociology*, 11(4), 230. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14254/2071789X.2018/11-4/15>
- Hepfner, A. S. (2017). The Difference in Job Satisfaction between Full-Time and Part-Time Early Childhood Educators Working in Public and Private Schools in South Carolina. ProQuest Dissertations Publishing, (Order No. 10266121). <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/difference-job-satisfaction-betweenfull-time/docview/1895131448/se-2?accountid=193930>
- Herzberg, F., *Work and the Nature of Man*. Cleveland, World Publishing Company, 1966.
- Holman, D. and Axtell, C. (2016), “Can job redesign interventions influence a broad range of employee outcomes by changing multiple job characteristics? A quasi-experimental study”, *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, Vol. 21 No. 3, pp. 284-295.
- Homyamyen, P., Kulachai, W., & Phuangthuean, P. (2017). Impacts of non-financial factors on job satisfaction of public schools' teachers. *International Journal of Arts & Sciences*, 10(2), 467-474.
- Ibrahim, R.Z.A.R.; Zalam, W.Z.M.; Foster, B.; Afrizal, T.; Johansyah, M.D.; Saputra, J.; Bakar, A.A.; Dagang, M.M.; Ali, S.N.M. (2021). Psychosocial Work Environment and Teachers’ Psychological Well-Being: The Moderating Role of Job Control and Social Support. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2021, 18, 7308. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18147308>
- Jackson, M. J. (2018). Examining the Relationship between School Climate and Teacher Absenteeism, Teacher Job Satisfaction, and Teachers' Intentions to Remain. ProQuest Dissertations Publishing, (Order No. 10846881). <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/examining-relationship-between-schoolclimate/docview/2117016963/se-2?accountid=193930>
- Javier, E.R. and Deligero, J.C.L. (2014) Job Satisfaction of the Teaching and Non-Teaching Staff of the Lyceum of the Philippines University—Batangas. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 6, 1-10.
- Kalaw, J.F. (2014) Organizational Culture among Teaching Employees of Lyceum of the Philippines University—Batangas: Basis of Enhancement. *International Journal of Information, Business and Management*, 6, 52-66.
- Kanesan, A. G. & Ling, Y. (2018). Teachers’ Work Value towards Workplace Culture in Educational Organization of Malaysia. *International Journal of Management Studies*. V(2(5)):36 DOI:10.18843/ijms/v5i2(5)/05
- Kasalak, G. & Dağyar, M. (2020). The Relationship between Teacher Self-Efficacy and Teacher Job Satisfaction: A Meta-Analysis of the Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS). *Kuram Ve Uygulamada Egitim Bilimleri*, 20(3), 16-33. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12738/jestp.2020.3.002>
- Klassen, R., Yerdelen, S., & Durksen, T. (2013). Measuring Teacher Engagement: Development of the Engaged Teachers Scale (ETS). *Frontline Learning Research*, 1(2). doi: 10.14786/flr.v1i2.44
- Klecker, B., & Loadman, W. (2011). Exploring the relationship between teachers’ empowerment and teachers’ job satisfaction. *Midwestern Educational Research Association*.
- Komagata, M., Takemura, Y., Ichikawa, N., Takehara, K., & Kunie, K. (2020). Quality of work among part-time nurses and its relationship to job satisfaction and work values: A cross-sectional study. *Nursing and Health Sciences*, 22(4), 1010-1021.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/nhs.12760>

Kraft, M. A., Simon, N. S., & Lyon, M. A. (2020). Sustaining a Sense of Success: The Importance of Teacher Working Conditions During the COVID-19 Pandemic. (EdWorkingPaper: 20-279). Retrieved from Annenberg Institute at Brown University: <https://doi.org/10.26300/35nj-v890>

Kuncoro, T. and Dardiri, A. (2017). Teacher Performance and Work Environment in the Instructional Process in Vocational School. AIP Conference Proceedings 1887, 020043 (2017); <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5003526>

Lyubomirsky, S., & Layous, K. (2013). How do simple positive activities increase well-being? *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 22(1), 57–62. doi:10.1177/0963721412469809.

Mart, C. T. (2013). A passionate teacher: Teacher commitment and dedication to student learning. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 2(1), 437-442.

Masoom, M. R. (2021). "Teachers' Perception of Their Work Environment: Evidence from the Primary and Secondary Schools of Bangladesh", *Education Research International*, vol. 2021, Article ID 4787558, 12 pages, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/4787558> Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (uni.edu)

Misu, S I. (2020). Teacher's Work Engagement – Change and Adaptation During Covid-19 Pandemic. *Business Excellence and Management*. Vol 10 Special Issue 1 October 2020.

Niemi, P.H. M. & Kousa, P. (2021). A Case Study of Students' and Teachers' Perceptions in a Finnish High School during the COVID. *International Journal of Technology in Education and Science* Volume 4, Issue 4, Fall 2020 ISSN: 2651-5369

Obineli, S.A, (2013). Teachers' perception of the factors affecting job satisfaction in Ekwusigo Local Government of Anambra State, Nigeria. *African Research Review: An International Multidisciplinary Journal*, Ethiopia, 7 (4-31), 225-237. Doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/afrev.7i4.13>

Okonkwo, M.C. & Obineli S.A. (2011). The Roles of counselling in promoting good leadership: Anambra state on the focus. *Review of Behavioural Sciences (JRBS)*, 3(1), 144-153.

Orth, M. and Volmer, J. (2017), "Daily within-person effects of job autonomy and work engagement on innovative behaviour: the cross-level moderating role of creative self-efficacy", *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 26 No. 4, pp. 601-612.

Oubibi, M.; Fute, A.; Xiao, W.; Sun, B.; Zhou, Y. Perceived Organizational Support and Career Satisfaction among Chinese Teachers: The Mediation Effects of Job Crafting and Work Engagement during COVID-19. *Sustainability* 2022, 14, 623. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14020623>

Parent-Lamarche, A. Teleworking, Work Engagement, and Intention to Quit during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Same Storm, Different Boats? *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 2022, 19, 1267. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19031267>

Perera, H., Vosicka, L., Granziera, H., & McIlveen, P. (2018). Towards an integrative perspective on the structure of teacher work engagement. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 108, 28-41. doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2018.05.006

Prince, J. J. (2020). Relationship of Principal Positivity with Teacher Job Satisfaction and Staff Morale. ProQuest Dissertations Publishing, (Order No. 27994797).

Sahito, Z. & Vaisanen, P. (2017). Factors Affecting Job Satisfaction of Teacher Educators: Empirical Evidence from the Universities of Sindh Province of Pakistan. *Journal of Teacher Education and Educators* Volume 6, Number 1, 2017, 5-30.

Schaufeli, W., Salanova, M., Gonzalez-Roma, V., & Bakker, A. (2002). The Measurement of Engagement and Burnout: a Two Sample Confirmatory Factor Analytic Approach. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 3, 71–92. doi:10.1023/A:1015630930326.

Simeon, L. M. (2021). ADB: Teachers need more government support. *The Philippine Star*. ADB: Teachers need more government support | Philstar.com Retrieved on January 20, 2021.

Sokal, L. J., Trudel, L. G. E., and Babb, J. C. (2020). Supporting Teachers in Times of Change: The Job Demands- Resources Model and Teacher Burnout During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Contemporary Education* Vol. 3, No. 2; October 2020 ISSN 2575-3177 E-ISSN 2575-3185

Stone, C. & Springer, M. (2019). Interactivity, connectedness and "teacher-presence": Engaging and retaining students online. *Australian Journal of Adult Learning*, 59(2), 146-169.

Sultan, G. A. (2020). Administrative empowerment among Kuwait University staff and its effect on their job satisfaction. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 12(2), 210-229. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/JARHE-02-2019-0027>

Tims, M., Bakker, A.B. and Xanthopoulou, D. (2011), “Do transformational leaders enhance their followers’ daily work engagement?”, *The Leadership Quarterly*, Vol. 22 No. 1, pp. 121-131.

Tims, M., Bakker, A.B., Derks, D. and Van Rhenen, W. (2013), “Job crafting at the team and Organization Management, Vol. 38 No. 4, pp. 427-454.

Tobias, L. J. (2017). A Study of Teacher Job Satisfaction, Teacher Preferred Leadership Behaviors, and the Impact of the Leadership Behaviors on Teacher Job Satisfaction. ProQuest Dissertations Publishing, (Order No. 10278623). <https://www.proquest.com/dissertations-theses/study-teacher-job-satisfactionpreferred/docview/1920174267/se-2?accountid=193930>

Trust, T., & Whalen, J. (2020). Should teachers be trained in emergency remote teaching? Lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Technology and Teacher Education*, 28(2), 189-199. Retrieved from <https://www.learntechlib.org/primary/p/215995/>.

Tuckey, M.R., Bakker, A.B. and Dollard, M.F. (2012), “Empowering leaders optimize working conditions for engagement: a multilevel study”, *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, Vol. 17 No. 1, pp. 15-27.

Uzun, Tevfik; Ozdem, Güven (2017). The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction on the Relationship between Teachers' Perceptions of Supervisor Support and Job Performances <https://eric.ed.gov/?q=job+satisfaction+studies&pg=5&id=EJ1148390>

Van Mierlo, H. and Bakker, A.B. (2018), “Crossover of engagement in groups”, *Career Development International*, Vol. 23 No. 1, pp. 106-118

Van Wingerden, J., & Poell, R. (2019). Meaningful work and resilience among teachers: The mediating role of work engagement and job crafting. *PLOS ONE*, 14(9), e0222518. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0222518

Vipinosa, L. D. & Acevedo, C. G. F. (2015). MLI. Productivity, Work Values, and Teaching Effectiveness of Science Teachers in Capiz State University. *Educational Quest: An Int. J. of Education and Applied Social Sciences* Vol 6 | Issue 2 | August 2015

Ye, Z., Liu, H., & Gu, J. (2019). Relationships between conflicts and employee perceived job performance: Job satisfaction as mediator and collectivism as moderator. *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 30(5), 706-728. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/IJCM-01-2019-0010>

Yerdelen, S., Durksen, T., & Klassen, R. (2018). An international validation of the engaged teacher scale. *Teachers And Teaching*, 24(6): 673-689. doi: 10.1080/13540602.2018.1457024

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Buenafe C. Cadampog

Notre Dame Of Midsayap College – Philippines

Dr. Oldric J. Licaros

Notre Dame Of Midsayap College – Philippines